

1 **Theoretical dilemmas, conceptual review and perspectives disclosure of**
2 **the sharing economy: A qualitative analysis**
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18
19 **Abstract**

20 The sharing economy (SE) has become a prominent theme in a broad variety of research domains in
21 the last decade. With conceptions from an increasing range of theoretical perspectives, SE literature
22 is disperse and disconnected, with a great proliferation of definitions and related terms which hinder
23 organized and harmonious research. This study carries out a systematic literature review from 1978
24 to September 2020, uncovering 50 definitions as units of analysis. The authors, through a
25 qualitative-interpretative analysis, review definitions, identify perspectives, and critically assess
26 their conceptual nature on an evolutionary basis. Findings show that despite the SE has been
27 extending its routes and approaches, it is far from a stock of conceptual grounds. The paper makes
28 three contributions. First, we portray SE within a common evolutionary framework by developing it
29 as a life cycle model. Second, we clarify the definitional and terminological jungle. And third, we
30 suggest a new definition that can enrich the discussion.

31 **Keywords:** Sharing economy; Systematic literature review; Qualitative interpretative analysis;
32 Theory development; Umbrella concept

33 **JEL Classification:** M190 · M300 · O35 · L260
34

35 **1 Introduction**

36 Sharing economy research faces an uncontrolled emergence of related terms and definitions, due to
37 its rise to the forefront of entrepreneurship, innovation, technology and management (Bouncken et
38 al., 2020; Bouncken and Reuschl 2018; Muñoz and Cohen 2017). This has triggered a proliferation

39 of contributions, continuously expanding its nature and scope. This growth is not without
40 controversy, in part because of the diversity of approaches and definitions (Filser et al. 2020;
41 Hossain 2020; Paik et al. 2019), in part because of its profound economic, social, legal and political
42 implications (Codagnone and Martens 2016), in addition to the limited empirical contributions
43 (Laurenti et al. 2019), which have led to contradiction, confusion, and complexity surrounding its
44 identity. Therefore, this study aims to contribute to determining the nature and scope of the SE
45 through examining the conceptual evolution, by organizing definitions and terms, identifying
46 perspectives, and providing an evolutionary framework to facilitate theory development and guide
47 future research.

48 Beyond the interest to study the SE at an institutional level (European Commission 2017 2018; U.S.
49 Department of the Treasury 2019), the economic and social relevance of the increasingly employed
50 activities encompassed within the SE is unquestionable. To mention some examples, 26% of U.S.
51 Internet users participated in SE services and these figures are predicted to rise to 41% in 2021
52 (eMarketer 2019). Further, the number of active “peer-to-peer” or sharing platforms in the Europe
53 Union in 2017 was around 500, of which at least 4% were considered to be extremely significant, as
54 they received more than 100,000 visits a day, generating revenues of more than \$4,000 million and
55 facilitating transactions of more than \$25,000 million (European Commission 2017).

56 At the academic level, the growing relevance of the SE is undeniable, and this is reflected from
57 various points of view. In the Web of Science (WoS) database alone, about 1,400 articles and
58 reviews addressing SE-related topics can be found until 15 September 2020, of which more than
59 87% have been published since 2017. These articles have been published in more than 390 journals,
60 which also shows the growing demand for journals that are open to publishing work in this area.
61 Moreover, these publications relate to very diverse research domains, such as business,
62 management, tourism and hospitality, environmental sciences, computer science, economics, and to
63 a lesser extent to areas such as legal sciences, urban planning and development, and sociology.

64 But what has been happening with the SE? After the first and occasional contribution on the SE at
65 the end of the 1970s (Felson and Spaeth 1978), there followed a period of lack of interest in this
66 concept, which then rose to the very cutting edge of management in the late 2000s, 2010s and has
67 continued rising until today, linked not only to the proliferation of companies and SE activities but
68 also as a social phenomenon (Botsman and Rogers 2010). Thus, on the positive side, from 2010
69 onwards, there has been an explosion of research work, continuing to this day, which has increased
70 the understanding of various consumer, business and government behaviors around the practices,
71 production, and consumption derived from SE-businesses (Eckhardt et al. 2019; Hossain 2020).
72 Despite this outburst, scholars have not fully agreed upon either a definition of the sharing economy
73 or a framework to guide further research, and we continue to miss the ‘big’ picture. The problem
74 seems to be that extant previous theoretical analyses of the SE have focused on analyzing
75 transversal issues common to many SE activities, such as for example, examining the role of digital

76 platforms (Sutherland and Jarrahi 2018), assessing the competitive effects (Zervas et al. 2017), or
77 identifying the sustainability basis of the concept (Curtis and Lehner 2019). Thus, under the
78 concept sharing economy, we find disconnected literature which prompts a floating state of the SE
79 conceptual framework. Thus, although bibliometric (e.g. Filser et al. 2020; Laurenti et al. 2019) and
80 systematic (e.g. Curtis and Lehner 2019; Hossain 2020) review studies have been carried out in
81 recent years that had helped to study the nature and scope of the SE, these works have focused
82 mainly on studying this field from a quantitative exploration of published papers features, or on
83 general analysis of extant literature in this field. As a step further, due to the fuzziness about the SE
84 concept, present work aims to bring light on its conceptual underpinnings and evolution as
85 scientific field based on a systematic literature review and qualitative analysis.

86 In this regard, this paper follows the call for context-specific research to understand what and how
87 to study (Petigrew 2005), reviewing existing contributions and definitions (Sweeney et al. 2019).
88 Thus, it is necessary to conduct a selected literature review that “summarizes the primary research,
89 but each also goes further, providing readers with a strong organizational framework and careful
90 analysis” (Cropanzano 2009: p. 2009), providing a construct clarification to extant theory, and
91 being a “unique opportunity for developing novel and engaging theoretical ideas and constructs,
92 based on informed understandings of past research” (Post et al. 2020: pp. 370–371).

93 Under this premise, several reasons support this study. Firstly, at an epistemological level we
94 should consider whether we are facing the emergence of a new area of study. As Starbuck (2009: p.
95 108) points out, “the social and behavioral sciences contain a myriad of conceptual and
96 methodological fad sequences”. Beyond the constant search for novel topics, mass production of
97 research, the search for generalizations, or disagreement on the validity of applicable theories and
98 methods (Starbuck 2009), the diversity of approaches and disciplines applicable to a topic drives
99 the approach to new questions and the incorporation of new methods and theories (Abrahamson
100 2009). The SE is not exempt from debates about its nature and functioning that may undermine it as
101 an area of study or categorize it as just as a fad. Questions arise such as whether it is based on
102 sharing versus exchange or giving (Belk 2010), whether a new consumer paradigm (Prothero et al.,
103 2011), whether it generates competitive rivalry or not (Lamberton and Rose 2012), whether it is an
104 opportunity for entrepreneurship (Bouncken et al., 2020; Cohen and Kietzmann 2014), whether it
105 empowers innovation (Bouncken et al., 2020), whether it develops in bilateral or multilateral
106 markets (Codagnone and Martens 2016), whether it is a new form of lobbying (Codagnone et al.
107 2016), or rather a manifestation of neoliberal capitalism (Martin 2016), whether it is prior to or a
108 consequence of the Internet (Frenken and Schor 2017), whether it is an essentially technological
109 concept (Puschmann and Alt 2016), whether it is a new business model (Kumar et al. 2018) and if
110 yes, what exactly entails a sharing economy business model (Ritter and Schanz 2019), whether if
111 SE businesses disrupt prevailing institutions (Zvolska et al. 2019), whether if customers are
112 energetically looking for the social aspects of SE platforms as they go beyond the classic B2C

113 offerings (Clauss et al., 2018), whether it allows to sell authentic experiences (Bucher et al., 2018),
114 if it affects other existing activities (Zervas et al. 2017), if it requires legal changes (European
115 Commission 2018; Smorto 2018), if trust is a requirement for implementation (Hawlitschek et al.
116 2018), if service providers are suppliers or employees (Hagiu and Wright 2019), or even if it should
117 be considered as a path to sustainability (Curtis and Lehner 2019).

118 Secondly, it is a multidisciplinary area of study to which contributions have been made from many
119 different areas, both academic (e.g., Laurenti et al. 2019) and professional (e.g., Deloitte 2016),
120 institutional or legal (Smorto 2018), which has elicited a rich concept but, simultaneously,
121 fragmented, diffuse, with terminological confusions (Curtis and Lehner 2019) and with an
122 unanalyzed definitional dilemma (Hossain 2020). For the sake of theory development, the lacking
123 of consensus requires a work of “tidying up” of definitions and concepts (Hirsch and Levin 1999).

124 Thirdly, from the theory development, the concept of SE traces a life-cycle in the process of
125 consolidation with an intense variety and conceptual heterogeneity that is necessary to put in order
126 (Hirsch and Levin 1999). Because of its relative novelty and broad scope, it can be considered an
127 'umbrella' concept (Belk 2014; Perren and Kozinets 2018), although future empirical evidence
128 should provide specific validations.

129 Finally, the lack of consensus on the activities covered and the agents involved in the SE becomes
130 an uphill climb to arrive at a shared definition. There are two reasons for this (Herbert and Collin-
131 Lachaud 2017). First, the practices described within the SE “extremely varied, flourishing,
132 constantly changing and subject to the fad effect” (p. 4). The second relates to the actors
133 themselves: “Out of pragmatism, they do not impose specific criteria or boundaries on the
134 transactions of the collaborative economy” (p. 4).

135 Therefore, our paper seeks to address these multiple disconnections by providing an integrated and
136 novel conceptual framework that sheds light on potential theoretical development. With this aim,
137 this study is carried out in three steps. First, a replicable process of identifying relevant SE
138 definitions is conducted through a systematic literature review. Then, following the prior discussion
139 of the terminology and definition proliferations, an interpretative analysis for disclosing underlying
140 perspectives is carried out, contributing to the literature with an evolutionary framework of SE
141 approaches. Finally, an SE definition is proposed, as well as a set of guidelines for future research
142 avenues.

143

144 **2 Methods**

145 To find all the definitions that have been applied to the SE, a systematic literature review (SLR)
146 was conducted. This approach enables any relevant studies to be selected and evaluated, ensuring a
147 structured, rigorous and replicable literature review, as well as obtaining a more objective overview
148 of the search results and eliminating any bias (Cropanzano 2009; Post et al. 2020; Tranfield et al.

149 2003). This is one of the main differences of this methodology with respect to a traditional narrative
150 review. To conduct the SLR, we based on Tranfield et al. (2003)'s stages (see Figure 1).

151

152 **2.1 Planning the review**

153 Once identified the need for a review of the term “sharing economy” due to the great contradiction,
154 confusion, and complexity surrounding it in the academic literature and its identity (Curtis and
155 Lehner 2019; Hossain 2020), we state the research problem and the objectives, define the scope and
156 establish a review protocol for our study considering the guidelines that will ensure the quality of
157 the review (Snyder 2019; Sweeney et al. 2019). Accordingly, as search boundaries, the Web of
158 Science Core Collection was chosen as database for this research, since it is recognized as the most
159 important and longest standing database of academic papers (Mongeon and Paul-Hus 2016; Vogel
160 and Güttel 2012). The search period was limited to manuscripts published in English between 1978
161 and 15 September 2020, since it was in 1978 when the first article relating to SE appeared (cf.
162 Felson and Spaeth 1978).

163 Following the review protocol, a keyword search template was developed to account for all possible
164 SE-related terms. Thus, as suggested by previous articles (e.g., Curtis and Lehner 2019; Keathley-
165 Herring et al. 2016), a scoping study was developed to select the search terms that would be used
166 for the database search. Using the term “sharing economy” as a search query, the twenty most cited
167 articles in the WoS database were analyzed to conduct our scoping. By examining these studies, the
168 scoping study allowed us to detect seven related terms (sharing economy, collaborative
169 consumption, collaborative economy, peer to peer economy, access-based consumption,
170 commercial sharing systems, and lateral exchange markets), which were utilized to carry out the
171 subsequent search.

172 Furthermore, as preliminary inclusion criteria, we filtered for articles and review papers published
173 in academic journals due to their validated knowledge (Podsakoff et al. 2005), and therefore we
174 excluded conference proceedings, books and book chapters due to the lack of clarity in the peer
175 review processes and more restricted accessibility (Jones et al. 2011). However, considering the
176 novelty and breadth of areas linked to the SE, those books that are thematic pillars of the field were
177 checked along with this search (Dahlander and Gann 2010).

Fig 1 Analytical process implemented

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183 **2.2 Conducting the review**

184 The database search results returned 1,420 articles (see Table 1).

185

186 **Table 1** Search terms and returned results.

Term	Articles until 15 September 2020
“sharing economy”	1316
“collaborative consumption”	296
“collaborative economy”	75
“access-based consumption”	46
“peer to peer economy” OR “peer-to-peer economy” OR “P2P economy”	14
“commercial sharing systems”	3
“lateral exchange markets”	2
Avoiding duplicates	1.420

187 **Source:** WoS Core Collection – SSCI, SCI-Expanded, and AandHCI

188

189 From this point, the research followed two stages to ensure the purification of the database. In the
190 first stage, title, abstract, and keywords were revised to determine their suitability for inclusion,
191 taking into account the objectives and scope of this research. Articles that had the SE as their core
192 topic and that fitted the objectives and scope met the criteria for inclusion for suitability, while
193 articles that did not have the SE as a central theme or did not fit the objectives and scope, were
194 excluded on grounds of unsuitability (Snyder 2019; Tranfield et al. 2003). This stage ended with
195 the exclusion of 1,104 articles, and the inclusion of 316 articles. Then, during the second phase, the
196 full text of each of the articles considered relevant was examined to identify those articles that had a
197 definition of the sharing economy, thus all articles that did not offer a definition or that used
198 previously established definitions were excluded (scope inclusion/exclusion criteria). For this step,
199 a predatory reading approach was taken, focusing on the main parts of each article where
200 definitions in this area could be found (Curtis and Lehner 2019). As a result, a total of 44 articles
201 that defined SE were obtained. Additionally, it was decided to include 6 definitions manually.
202 These were found in thematic pillar books and were added as the definitions have been frequently
203 cited in articles of great impact (Dahlander and Gann 2010). Therefore, our final sample included
204 50 documents that defined the SE.

205

206 **2.3 Qualitative analysis**

207 From this point, our unit of analysis comprised 50 definitions of the SE. Building on principles of
208 thematic analysis, which is an interpretive synthesizing approach that enables a flexible and useful
209 research approach to examine qualitative data (Braun and Clarke 2006) and that facilitates an
210 improvement in the quality of literature reviews (Tranfield et al. 2003), we inductively identify,
211 analyze and report patterns from the data, where our “data” are the definitions and the recognized
212 patterns are the perspectives. Following the guidelines of Jones et al. (2011), the perspectives were

213 not extracted from decontextualized information as is commonly done but rather we inducted and
214 interpreted perspectives from our holistic understanding of each definition. The legitimacy for this
215 approach is based on the entangled nature, relative youth, and rapid development of the vocabulary
216 used in this scientific area. Furthermore, in thematic analysis patterns (in our case approaches)
217 could be identified either at a semantic or at a latent level (Boyatzis, 1998). At the semantic level,
218 patterns are identified in the explicit and superficial meaning of the data, without looking beyond
219 what is written, while in the latent approach the analyst goes beyond the semantic content of the
220 data, and discovers the underlying ideas, presumptions, and concepts that are theorized to form the
221 semantic content (Braun and Clarke 2006). In this way, we were able to identify both semantic and
222 latent perspectives in the definitions of SE.

223 The thematic analysis was divided into three steps, namely open, axial, and selective coding
224 (Gallicano 2013). During open coding, academics should read through the data several times and
225 then begin to create tentative labels for pieces of data that summarize what they have seen (without
226 the bias of existing theory -and limiting their focus to the meaning that emerges from the data)
227 (Corbin and Strauss 2015). Thus, we carefully examined all 50 definitions, decomposed them into
228 the smallest conceptual components, and converted data into concepts. This first approximation
229 resulted in a great number of finely grained concepts. Several sessions were needed to refine and
230 group any similar concepts into the same category to reduce the number of units that should be
231 further examined. Axial coding consists of identifying relationships from among the concepts of
232 each category, i.e. to categorize findings and look for commonalities and differences. Thus, during
233 this phase, we first ascertained the dominant concepts of each category and rearranged the data set
234 to form an ontological organization of the domain (Jones et al. 2011). Redundant concepts were
235 eliminated and the most representative concepts were selected. Then, as suggested by Corbin and
236 Strauss (2015) we verified the internal cohesion, consistency, and differentiation of each dominant
237 and dependent concept.

238 Finally, in the selective coding, researchers had to figure out the core concept that includes all of
239 the data of each category and selectively code any data that relates to the key concept identified.
240 Thus, in this step we examined all concepts of each category to determine the central explanatory
241 concept; therefore, we refined categories by condensing or expanding their focus (Corbin and
242 Strauss 2015). Iteration continued until we arrived at key categories with internal homogeneity and
243 external heterogeneity. Key categories are understood as core components of a phenomenon
244 (Kenny and Fourie 2015) and thus could be described as the perspectives under which a construct
245 has been studied.

246

247 **2.4 Organization of results**

248 The systematic literature review ended with the identification of 50 SE definitions, and thematic
249 analysis resulted in the discovery of 9 perspectives; these are *economic efficiency*, *government of*

250 *exchanges, technological, business model, consumer culture, environmental sustainability, social*
251 *orientation, value creation, and production system.* The collection of definitions has allowed us to
252 examine the terminological blossoming, definitional dilemma, that is to say, to unmask the
253 appearance of new similar terms and the development of these definitions. For its part, the
254 identification of 9 perspectives allowed us to analyze how many of them are present in each of the
255 definitions covered, to graph and examine the appearance of each perspective over time, and to
256 establish a description of each one of them.

257

258 **3 Conceptual contend: Towards a life-cycle model of the SE**

259 **3.1 A terminological blossoming**

260 The SE concept has elicited a wide range of related terminology, energized by its use in diverse
261 disciplines, and boosted by its rapid proliferation across industries. The SE concept was first coined
262 and defined by Felson and Spaeth (1978) under the term '*collaborative consumption*' which
263 reflected the social origin of the concept and, in fact, this was the only recognized conception for 30
264 years. With renewed interest in this subject, and with a similar conception Benkler (2004)
265 introduced and then Belk (2007) extended the term 'sharing'. Subsequently, new approaches with
266 an explicit extension of the scope of this field were introduced, generating, in turn, different
267 terminologies. Therefore, '*The mesh*' emerged as a term to account for a new logic of business
268 (Gansky 2010), and other terms such as '*access-based consumption*' (Bardhi and Eckhardt 2012)
269 and '*commercial sharing systems*' (Lamberton and Rose 2012) flourished with a sales and
270 marketing orientation. Moreover, although the term 'sharing economy' appears in the literature on
271 solidarity and economic geography (Gold 2004), Heinrichs (2013) applies the term '*sharing*
272 *economy*' in the context of sustainable exchanges. Additionally, the term '*collaborative economy*'
273 is introduced by Botsman (2014), while Schor and Fitzmaurice (2015) and Tussyadiah and Pesonen
274 (2016) focus their definitions on the term '*peer economy*', also '*P2P economy*', or '*economy of*
275 *equals*'.

276 However, the proliferation of terminology does not end here but has manifested itself with other
277 nearby terms that have declined in frequency, such as '*on-demand services*' or '*services on*
278 *demand*' (Benkler 2004), '*on-demand economy*' (Cockayne 2016; Sundararajan 2017), '*gig*
279 *economy*' (Martin 2016), '*temporary economy*' (Sundararajan 2013), '*platform economy*' (Kenney
280 and Zysman 2016), '*crowdfunding*' (Belleflamme et al. 2014) or '*gift economy*' (Cheal 1988).
281 Other focused terms used are '*microtask*', '*microwork*', '*micro-tasking*', or '*micro-working*'
282 (Sutherland and Jarrahi 2018). Besides, recently, the set of activities involving the SE has become
283 generalized in economic terms as '*lateral exchange markets*' (Perren and Kozinets 2018).

284 All this terminological flowering is a reflection of the of the SE becoming an umbrella term
285 (Acquier et al. 2017; Ryu et al. 2019), and being confirmed as the most widespread term (Table 1).

286

287 **3.2 A definitional dilemma**

288 The conceptual history of the SE concept took off after the publication of an American Behavioral
289 Scientist article by Felson and Spaeth (1978). They define collaborative consumption as “those
290 events in which one or more persons consume economic goods or services in the process of
291 engaging in joint activities with one or more others” (Felson and Spaeth 1978: p. 614). Thus, the
292 concept has its main roots in the human ecological theory of community structure and therefore has
293 a strong social perspective. It is not until almost three decades later that Benkler (2004) takes it up
294 again and redefines this concept, although maintaining the social perspective of it. Hereon, several
295 additional attempts to define, characterize, or describe SE have been made during the last fifteen
296 years. Thus, our systematic literature review allowed us to identify up to a total of 50 unique
297 definitions of SE (see summary in Appendix). This great diversity of definitions comes from many
298 different perspectives, which also indicates an absence of an agreed definition of what SE
299 represents.

300 To assess how these definitions have been adopted by academics, the citation count is analyzed. For
301 the case of definitions published in WoS journals, the most relevant definitions are those contained
302 in the works of Belk (2014), Hamari et al. (2016), and Bardhi and Eckhardt (2012). Moreover, the
303 work of Frenken and Schor (2017), despite being relatively recent, receives a not insignificant
304 number of citations. On the other side, from definitions contained in books, the most cited
305 according to Google Scholar are Botsman and Rogers (2010), and Lessig (2008). The dilemma
306 arises because the various definitions are different in nature, so opting for one or other of them
307 implies unbalancing the ‘umbrella’ nature of the SE concept. Then, the concept can become
308 conceptually asymmetrical, and therefore has brought with it the consequent loss of scope. So much
309 so that an outstanding feature of the literature is that many works use the concept of the SE without
310 explicitly defining it. However, while choosing one or the other supposes narrowing the meaning,
311 this could ultimately formulate more specific problems.

312 It is undeniable that the conceptualizations of social science phenomena must possess a balance
313 between generality, simplicity, and precision (Weick 1979). Undoubtedly, certain definitions have
314 been relevant for the theoretical development of the SE by incorporating new routes to its
315 understanding. However, by focusing mainly on particular perspectives, but leaving aside others,
316 these definitions have gained in simplicity but sacrificed precision. Thus, most tend to be unspecific
317 and at the same time too general. What is clear is that the most modern definitions cover more and
318 more views, which brings us closer to a more precise definition, but while these definitions are
319 promising, the SE remains confused and disconnected.

320

321 **3.3 Perspectives contend: A life-cycle model of the SE**

322 The multifaceted nature of the SE leads us to apply an interpretative synthesis approach (Braun and
323 Clarke 2006) to the above set of definitions. Thus, nine perspectives of the SE are uncovered in an

324 inductive manner (Jones et al. 2011). Interpretation is carried out at semantic and latent levels
325 (Boyatzis 1998). These nine routes are represented as distinctive characteristics within the
326 definitions (Kenny and Fourie 2015) (see Table 2).

Accepted for publication

Table 2 Links of the underlying perspectives of sharing economy to root terms

Author	Root term	Economic Efficiency	Government of exchanges	Technological	Business model	Consumer culture	Environmental sustainability	Social orientation	Value creation	Production system
Felson and Spaeth (1978)	Collaborative consumption					✓		✓✓		
Benkler (2004)	Sharing economy							✓✓		✓
Belk (2007)	Collaborative consumption			✓		✓✓				
Lessig (2008)	Collaborative consumption					✓✓				
Botsman and Rogers (2010)	Collaborative consumption	✓✓			✓✓			✓✓		
Bardhi and Eckhardt (2012)	Access-based consumption		✓✓			✓✓				
Lamberton and Rose (2012)	Commercial sharing systems	✓✓	✓✓		✓	✓✓				
Heinrichs (2013)	Sharing economy		✓✓	✓✓			✓			
Belk (2014)	Collaborative consumption	✓	✓✓	✓	✓✓	✓		✓		
Botsman (2014)	Collaborative economy	✓✓	✓✓			✓✓				
Schor and Fitzmaurice (2015)	Peer-to-Peer economy	✓✓	✓✓		✓✓	✓✓		✓✓		
Stephany (2015)	Sharing economy	✓✓		✓✓	✓	✓✓				
Aloni (2016)	Sharing economy	✓	✓✓	✓✓		✓				
Barnes and Mattsson (2016)	Collaborative consumption		✓✓	✓✓		✓				
Cockayne (2016)	Sharing economy			✓✓	✓					
European Comission	Collaborative economy		✓✓	✓✓	✓✓	✓✓				

(2016)								
Hamari <i>et al.</i> (2016)	Sharing economy		✓✓	✓	✓			
Kathan <i>et al.</i> (2016)	Sharing economy	✓✓	✓	✓	✓✓	✓		
Puschmann and Alt (2016)	Sharing economy		✓✓	✓✓	✓✓	✓✓		✓
Shaheen <i>et al.</i> (2016)	Sharing economy				✓✓			
Tussyadiah and Pesonen (2016)	Peer-to-Peer economy		✓✓	✓		✓✓		✓✓
Sundararajan (2017)	Sharing economy		✓✓	✓✓				
Acquier <i>et al.</i> (2017)	Sharing economy	✓✓		✓✓				✓✓
Frenken y Schor (2017)	Sharing economy	✓✓	✓✓		✓✓	✓✓		
Habibi <i>et al.</i> (2017)	Sharing economy		✓✓			✓✓		
Muñoz and Cohen (2017)	Sharing economy	✓✓	✓✓	✓				
Arvidsson (2018)	Sharing economy	✓	✓				✓✓	✓
Perren and Kozinets (2018)	Lateral exchange markets		✓✓	✓✓	✓	✓		✓
Curtis and Lehner (2019)	Sharing economy			✓		✓	✓✓	✓
Dellaert (2019)	Sharing economy			✓	✓✓			✓✓
Eckhardt <i>et al.</i> (2019)	Sharing economy		✓	✓✓	✓✓	✓✓		✓✓
Guyader and Piscicelli (2019)	Sharing economy	✓✓	✓✓	✓✓	✓✓	✓✓		✓✓
Davlembayeva <i>et al.</i> (2019)	Sharing economy		✓✓	✓✓	✓✓	✓		✓✓
Wang <i>et al.</i> (2019)	Sharing economy	✓✓	✓✓	✓✓	✓✓			

Gao and Li (2020)				✓✓		✓✓		✓
Gerwe and Silva (2020)		✓✓	✓	✓✓	✓	✓✓	✓	
Akhmedova, Mas-Machuca, and Marimon (2020)		✓✓	✓✓	✓✓	✓	✓✓	✓✓	✓✓
Govindan, Shankar and Kannan (2020)		✓	✓	✓✓	✓✓		✓	✓✓
Yu, Xu, Yu, Sang, Yang and Jiang (2020)				✓✓		✓	✓	✓✓
Sanasi et al. (2020)	Sharing economy	✓	✓✓	✓✓	✓✓	✓✓		✓✓
Berg et al. (2020)	Peer-to-Peer economy		✓✓	✓✓		✓✓		✓✓
Fahmy (2020)	Sharing economy	✓	✓✓	✓✓	✓✓	✓		✓
Curtis and Mont (2020)	Sharing economy	✓✓	✓✓	✓✓	✓✓	✓✓	✓	✓
Hazée <i>et al.</i> (2020)	Collaborative consumption		✓✓	✓✓	✓	✓✓		✓
Kim and Kim (2020)	Sharing economy	✓✓	✓✓	✓	✓✓	✓		✓
Zmysłony <i>et al.</i> (2020)	Sharing economy	✓✓	✓✓	✓✓	✓✓	✓✓	✓	✓✓
Fielbaum and Tirachini (2020)	Sharing economy	✓✓	✓✓	✓✓			✓	
Huang and Kuo (2020)	Sharing economy	✓✓	✓✓	✓✓	✓✓		✓	✓
Lee (2020)	Sharing economy	✓✓	✓✓	✓✓	✓✓			
Wu and Yan (2020)	Sharing economy		✓✓			✓✓		

328 ✓✓: Semantic level

329 ✓: Latent level

330 The perspectives are described as follows.
331

- 332 • *Economic efficiency*: use of underutilized goods and services in the most rational way
333 possible to avoid idle capacities.
- 334 • *Exchange governance*: way in which the good or service is accessed (e.g. peer-to-peer) and
335 the transaction is regulated (such as enhancing consumer rights, reducing information
336 asymmetries, reinforcing trust in the other party, and reducing transaction costs).
- 337 • *Technological*: an activity that is carried out through the intermediation of a technological
338 platform, such as web 3.0.
- 339 • *Business model*: generation of income for the person who cedes the use of the good or
340 service and, therefore, a for-profit modality, unlike other modalities that are free.
- 341 • *Consumer culture*: motivation that explains the consumption of a good or service only
342 when it is needed, without this implying access to the property.
- 343 • *Environmental sustainability*: more sustainable consumption practices as opposed to purely
344 market-based exchanges, taking advantage of idle capacities and/or facilitating access to the
345 property.
- 346 • *Social orientation*: systems of social exchange rather than allocation through markets where
347 there are a non-pecuniary motivation and social purpose.
- 348 • *Value creation*: generation of some physical or non-monetary utility for the individual who
349 demands the good or service (such as meeting people, having fun, saving time, consuming
350 on-demand or for convenience and comfort).
- *Production system*: production generation or a different mode of production.

351 The disruption of new perspectives has generated inflection points along with the concept life.
352 Using an evolutionary framework (Hirsch and Levin 1999), and focusing on a semantic level, we
353 develop a particularly distinctive evolution of the SE's life through four different stages (see Figure
354 2).

355 *The Inception period (1978-2008)*. The SE appears on the scene from a sociological perspective as a
356 justification for events where people consume goods or services together /in a group (Felson and
357 Spaeth 1978). However, despite the inception of the SE as an area of study in the late 1970s, this
358 phenomenon did not attract any attention until almost three decades later, when Benkler (2004)
359 takes up this idea by reopening the door for this phenomenon. The concept began to evolve, when
360 Belk (2007) and Lessig (2008) explicitly highlight the perspective of consumer culture, by
361 enhancing the non-proprietary access to these joint events. Thus, in a first period, although
362 extensive in time, but scarce in terms of the number of contributions, the SE showed a clear and
363 narrow focus on social orientation and consumer culture.

364

Fig. 2. An evolutionary framework of SE perspectives (number of definitions).

365

366

367

368 *The Transition period (2009-2012).* In the late 2000s and amid the global economic crisis, however,

369 the concept of SE began to be investigated more seriously and its transition began. The foundation

370 of companies like Airbnb (August 2008), Uber (March 2009) or the transformation of companies

371 such as Couchsurfing to a for-profit entity (May 2011) brings with it the expansion of the

372 perspectives of the SE, which it extends its range of essential routes to economic efficiency, new

373 business models and the governance of exchanges (Botsman and Rogers 2010; Bardhi and Eckhardt

374 2012). Thus, Botsman and Rogers (2010) highlight how the SE helps to address the underutilization

375 of assets and, therefore, their idle capacity. Bardhi and Eckardt (2012), stress the non-transfer of

376 ownership, while Lamberton and Rose (2012) add the rivalry of consumers for limited choice, and

377 Bardhi and Eckhardt (2012) and Lamberton and Rose (2012) are the first to introduce aspects

378 related to the transaction itself and the governance of exchanges. Thus, the approaches that

379 appeared in this period represented a promising advance in research on the SE, by suggesting a

380 broader theoretical framework.

381 *The Acceptance Excitement period (2013-2018).* After this transition, the SE begins a period of

382 acceptance that results in excitement to investigate this phenomenon from various perspectives and

383 this ultimately leads to this area receiving 21 definitions in just 6 years. This period involves the

384 acceptance of the five perspectives already established in the two previous periods (cf. Aloni 2016;

385 Frenken and Schor 2017; Perren and Kozinets 2018), but also continues to nurture the concept of

386 SE with two new perspectives. To such an extent the multiple perspectives of the concept can be
387 appreciated in the definition provided by Schor and Fitzmaurice (2015), which includes the most
388 common ones up to that moment, such as consumer culture, governance of exchanges, social
389 orientation, and economic efficiency, in addition to the business model perspective, which is
390 somewhat less common. However, with the arrival of web 3.0. in the early 2010s, the emergence of
391 smartphones, mobile applications, the Internet of things, and big data which it brought with it and
392 the rapid adoption of these by SE businesses (for example, Uber launched its mobile app in late
393 2011 and Airbnb in late 2012), almost immediately brought the inclusion of technology (digital
394 platforms) as an essential feature of the SE definitions (cf. Hamari et al. 2016; Heinrichs 2013).
395 Likewise, Tussyadiah and Pesonen (2016) add for the first time production systems as a new
396 perspective of the SE, which, however, still lacks development. While several perspectives were
397 accentuated during this period, the addition of new ones and the great emergence of definitions
398 resulted in a large but disconnected multifaceted area.

399 *The Maturity Challenge period (2019-to date)*. Finally, starting in 2019 and once the period of
400 acceptance excitement has ended, a period of maturity challenge begins, where new essential
401 perspectives appear that reflect new analysis trends and that expand the range of the SE, as is the
402 case of environmental sustainability and value creation. Thus, Curtis and Lehner (2019) introduce
403 in their definition the shared practices that promote sustainable consumption in the face of growing
404 concern about sustainability and environmental impact. On the other hand, Dellaert (2019) write
405 from the value creation perspective to denote the non-monetary demands that consumers expect to
406 receive when using SE goods or services (e.g., meeting people or having fun). Eckhardt et al.
407 (2019), without adding any new perspectives, reflect the importance of previous perspectives such
408 as consumer culture and the technological aspect surrounding the SE. The most significant changes
409 in this period are consolidation of SE as business model, the concern for the sustainability, the
410 relevance of the social orientation and the takeoff of the value creations and production system
411 perspectives.

412 And finally, in this process of challenging the maturity of the concept, Akhmedova et al. (2020),
413 Curtis and Mont (2020) and Zmysłony et al. (2020) propose the broadest and most ambitious
414 definitions that this area has received, incorporating seven out nine existing perspectives. Despite
415 these theoretical efforts, the field still possesses great complexities, contradictions, and confusion,
416 therefore it is undoubtedly time for a period of maturity challenge, where the SE is delineated, and
417 the doors are opened to more organized research that starts from a strong theoretical framework.

418 The nine approaches differ in the number of times they have been used to define the SE, varying
419 from the most common perspectives such as technological, consumer culture, and government of
420 exchanges, occurring in 37, 36, and 36 definitions respectively, to those that have a huge
421 discontinuity, such as value creation, the production system, and environmental sustainability,
422 occurring in 4, 8, and 10 definitions, respectively. The other three perspectives, which are less

423 commonly used, are the business model (29 occurrences), economic efficiency (25 occurrences),
424 and social orientation (21 occurrences). Not a single definition includes more than seven
425 perspectives (cf. Akhmedova et al. 2020, Curtis and Mont 2020, or Zmysłony et al. 2020), which
426 shows the existence of not complete definitions for the SE.

427

428 **4 Discussion and conclusions**

429 SE is an umbrella concept, of which 50 different definitions have been identified through a
430 systematic literature review. These have been associated with various root terms (access-based
431 consumption, collaborative economy, commercial sharing systems, sharing economy, collaborative
432 consumption, peer to peer economy, and lateral exchange markets). Considering the fuzziness of the
433 term, the terminology analysis reveals there is a dominant root term, namely, *sharing economy*, and
434 three followers, specifically *collaborative consumption*, *collaborative economy*, and *access-based*
435 *consumption*. Thus, it could be argued that there exists a denotative neologism with the term
436 *sharing economy*, for its use as Jack of all trades. From a linguistic point of view, this use is
437 justified, because it is the term mostly used in media, social networks, and even by the Internet
438 platforms to refer to themselves (e.g., Airbnb calls itself a ‘home-sharing service’). This, in turn,
439 has led to it being the most widely used term in academia (see Table 1) when referring to
440 collaborative practices. Thus, one would have to ask whether the term SE is used more for
441 popularity than for precision and consequently if there exist terms that are more accurate but less
442 popular for each specific activity that involves collaborative practices. In this regard, we propose
443 that a term such as collaborative economy is more appropriate when referring to the economic
444 efficiency of the term, access-based consumption better captures the consumer's perspective,
445 collaborative consumption could be more accurate to refer to the social nature of the concept, lateral
446 market exchanges gathers the technological framework of such exchanges, commercial sharing
447 systems is more precise when referring to the governance of exchanges present in the sharing
448 economy, and peer-to-peer focus more on the open nature of actors.

449 In a second step, a qualitative interpretative analysis of the definitions has shown the multifaceted
450 nature of the SE, with fragmented insights from different fields. As a result of this analysis, and as a
451 contribution to the literature, an evolutionary life framework of SE approaches through four
452 different stages is proposed. The disclosed approaches are *economic efficiency*, *government of*
453 *exchanges*, *technological*, *business model*, *consumer culture*, *environmental sustainability*, *social*
454 *orientation*, *value creation*, and *production system*. The analysis has not been limited to identifying
455 perspectives, but also semantic and latent layers have been stated. The proposed evolutionary life
456 framework shows how these approaches have appeared throughout the academic and professional
457 life of the SE. It explains how in the first incipient period (1978-2008) the SE was born from a
458 sociological point of view, going through a period of transition (2009-2012) with the arrival of the
459 world economic crisis and the emergence of new business models (e.g., Airbnb or Uber), extending

460 its focus in a period of excitement of acceptance (2013-2018) with the arrival of the technological
461 irruption and with the growing research on this phenomenon from various scientific areas, until
462 reaching the current state (2019-to date) of challenge of maturity, a period in which it is necessary
463 to focus on particular concerns of the SE.

464 The study also reveals the existence of a conceptual dilemma, in which specific positions can
465 contribute to gaining depth in the area of study, but at the cost of sacrificing generality and
466 precision. Therefore, findings evidence the need for a more balanced definition (Weick 1979). As a
467 consequence, a new definition of SE is proposed by including a comprehensive view of its nature.

468 The SE is understood as *business, production, and consumption sustainable*
469 *practices as value creation systems, which are based on temporary use of*
470 *underutilized assets, for free or for a fee, usually supported by digital platforms and*
471 *peer communities.*

472 Thus, in response to Acquier's (2017) statement that academics will probably never agree on a
473 definition of the SE since it is seen as an umbrella construct and is essentially controversial, this
474 definition indeed encompasses its rich nature. In this way, we intend to contribute to the literature
475 with a definition that can be used by academics regardless of their research position.

476 Several discussion matters, research gaps, and future research lines emanate from this work. From a
477 conceptual point of view, the SE concept has been evolving over the years, since although it was
478 born with an initial conception based mainly on social orientation, the most outstanding approaches
479 have been as consumer culture, technological, and government of exchanges. Thus, this concept has
480 been expanding its dimensionality, incorporating, in addition to the previous perspectives, an
481 orientation towards the business model, sustainability, and economic efficiency. So much so, that
482 the SE can be considered a vision of the organization of exchanges, alternative production system,
483 and consumption articulated on various interpretations. This in turn suggests a paradigmatic
484 configuration on a set of metaphors or perspectives, which leads to the consideration that the SE can
485 be seen as a paradigm in the economy (Arndt 1985). In this sense, it would be desirable to
486 investigate what is the trend of the SE in that square framework formed by the economic, social,
487 sustainable, and technological aspects of the SE. Consequently, it would be relevant to examine
488 towards which direction the SE is oriented, even more so given the crisis currently caused by the
489 COVID-19. In this context, several SE-companies (e.g. Airbnb) have already suffered a strong
490 economic impact (BBC News 2020) and the future of SE companies is, therefore, being questioned.
491 In this sense, the debate on policy-making about whether this type of company should be supported
492 and promoted at an institutional level due to its sustainability and social benefits takes on special
493 relevance (Codagnone and Martens 2016).

494 Furthermore, as one of the main contributions of this study is the disclosure of approaches and the
495 identification of the existence of these approaches in each definition both in a semantic and latent
496 way, this research can be a gateway for SE operationalization. In this way, as the SE is a growing

497 area of research, the theoretical contribution of this study opens the doors to academics from a wide
498 range of research areas to new perspectives to guide their research on SE. It is important to build a
499 conceptual framework that explains the development of SE-businesses from the components
500 identified in the literature. Thus, further research derived from this work evidences the need to
501 empirically corroborate and contrast in practice the perspectives proposed in this study, thereby
502 empirically testing a neglected area. Above all, the research needs to focus on specific problems of
503 the SE. e.g., the governance of SE companies, the image these companies have, and the problems
504 and conflicts regarding legal issues. Likewise, since SE businesses are mainly linked to services
505 (Bardhi and Eckhardt 2012; Hossain 2020), it would be relevant to delve more deeply into its
506 applicability and viability in the production of goods.

507 Finally, from a practical point of view, this article offers individual consumers, service providers,
508 regulatory authorities, companies in traditional sectors and SE companies, a holistic introduction to
509 the essential qualities of collaborative business.

510 This study is not exempt from some limitations. First, it only uses articles from academic journals
511 indexed in the Web of Science database, leaving out other databases (e.g., Scopus) as well as grey
512 literature. Secondly, as in any review work, the parameters for inclusion and exclusion of articles
513 influence the results. Thirdly, for the identification of perspectives an interpretative qualitative
514 approach was used, therefore as mentioned above it would be of interest to obtain empirical
515 contributions that corroborate the proposals included in this research.

516

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Date	Authors	Definition	Source	Citations
1978	Felson and Spaeth	“Acts of collaborative consumption, namely, those events in which one or more persons consume economic goods or services in the process of engaging in joint activities with one or more others” (p. 614).	<i>American Behavioral Scientist</i>	153
2004	Benkler	Refers to “sharing goods” as “a class of resources or goods that are amenable to being shared within social sharing systems rather than allocated through markets” (p. 356).	<i>Yale Law Journal</i>	321
2007	Belk	“Sharing is an alternative to the private ownership that is emphasized in both marketplace exchange and gift giving” (p. 127).	<i>The Annals of the American Academy of Political and Social Science</i>	267
2008	Lessig	“Collaborative consumption made by the activities of sharing, exchanging, and rental of resources without owning the goods” (p. 143).	<i>Remix: Making Art and Commerce Thrive in the Hybrid Economy</i>	3,264*
2010	Botsman and Rogers	“An economic model based for sharing underutilized assets for monetary or non-monetary benefits” (p. xv).	<i>What’s Mine Is Yours: The Rise of Collaborative Consumption</i>	4,363*
2012	Bardhi and Eckhardt	“Transactions that may be market mediated in which no transfer of ownership takes place” (p. 881).	<i>Journal of Consumer Research</i>	600
2012	Lamberton and Rose	“Marketer-managed systems that provide customers with the opportunity to enjoy product benefits without ownership. Importantly, these systems are characterized by between consumer rivalry for a limited supply of the shared product” (p. 109).	<i>Journal of Marketing</i>	289

2013	Heinrichs	“The concept (SE) involves individuals exchanging, redistributing, renting, sharing, and donating information, goods, and talent, either organizing themselves or via commercial organization by social media platforms” (p. 229).	<i>GAIA-Ecological Perspectives for Science and Society</i>	220
2014	Belk	“Collaborative consumption is people coordinating the acquisition and distribution of a resource for a fee or other compensation” (p. 1597).	<i>Journal of Business Research</i>	822
2014	Botsman	“The collaborative economy is a system that activates the untapped value of all kinds of assets through models and marketplaces that enable greater efficiency and access... increasingly those assets include... skills, utilities, and time” (p. 24).	<i>Harvard Business Review</i>	23
2015	Schor and Fitzmaurice	“Peer to peer sharing of access to underutilised goods and services, which prioritizes utilization and accessibility over ownership, either for free or for a fee” (p. 410).	<i>Handbook of Research on Sustainable Consumption</i>	99*
2015	Stephany	“The sharing economy is the value in taking underutilized assets and making them accessible online to a community, leading to a reduced need for ownership of those assets” (p. 9).	<i>The Business of Sharing - Making it in the New Sharing Economy</i>	363*
2016	Aloni	“An economic activity in which web platforms facilitate peer-to-peer exchanges of diverse types of goods and services” (p. 1398).	<i>Washington Law Review</i>	12
2016	Barnes and Mattsson	“The use of online marketplaces and social networking technologies to facilitate peer-to-peer sharing of resources (such as space, money, goods, skills and services) between individuals, who may be both suppliers and consumers” (p. 42).	<i>Technological. Forecasting and Social Change</i>	93

2016	Cockayne	“The on-demand or “sharing” economy is a term that describes digital platforms that connect consumers to a service or commodity through the use of a mobile application or website” (p. 73).	<i>Geoforum</i>	64
2016	European Commission	“It refers to business models in which activities are facilitated through collaborative platforms that create an open market for the temporary use of goods or services often offered by individuals” (p. 3).	<i>European Comission</i>	n.a.
2016	Hamari, Sjöklint and Ukkonen	“The sharing economy as an umbrella concept that encompasses several ICT developments and technologies, among others Collaborative Consumption, which endorses sharing the consumption of goods and services through online platforms” (p. 2047).	<i>Journal of the Association for Information Science and Technology</i>	729
2016	Kathan, Matzler and Veider	“This so-called sharing economy phenomenon is characterized by non-ownership, temporary access, and redistribution of material goods or less tangible assets such as money, space, or time” (p. 663).	<i>Business Horizons</i>	87
2016	Puschmann and Alt	“The use of an object (a physical good or service) whose consumption is split-up into single parts. These parts are collaborative consumed in C2C networks coordinated through community-based online services or through intermediaries in B2C models” (p. 95).	<i>Business Information Systems Engineering</i>	92
2016	Shaheen, Chan and Gaynor	“Sharing economy is a popularized term for consumption focused on access to goods and services through borrowing and renting rather than owning them” (p. 165)	<i>Transport Policy</i>	39
2016	Tussyadiah and	“A new socioeconomic system that allows	<i>Journal of Travel</i>	86

	Pesonen	for shared creation, production, distribution, and consumption of goods and resources among individuals” (p. 1022).	<i>Research</i>	
2017	Sundararajan	“The sharing economy is an economic system with the following five characteristics: largely market based, high impact capital, crowd based networks, blurring lines between the personal and professional, and blurring lines between fully employed and casual labor” (p. 23).	<i>The Sharing Economy: The End of Employment and the Rise of Crowd-Based Capitalism</i>	1,253*
2017	Acquier, Daudigeos and Pinkse	“Umbrella concept that rests on three foundational cores – (1) Access economy, (2) Platform economy, and (3) Community-based economy” (p. 1).	<i>Technological Forecasting and Social Change</i>	126
2017	Frenken and Schor	“Consumers granting each other temporary access to under-utilized physical assets (idle capacity), possibly for money” (pp. 4-5).	<i>Environmental Innovation and Societal Transitions</i>	243
2017	Habibi, Davidson and Laroche	“Non-ownership forms of consumption activities such as swapping, bartering, trading, renting, sharing and exchanging” (p. 113).	<i>Business Horizons</i>	67
2017	Muñoz and Cohen	“A socioeconomic system enabling an intermediated set of exchanges of goods and services between individuals and organizations which aim to increase efficiency and optimization of under-utilized resources in society” (p. 21).	<i>Technological Forecasting and Social Change</i>	74
2018	Arvidsson	“A new arena of economic action that builds...on common resources that are in themselves not directly susceptible to market exchange” (p. 289).	<i>Sociological Review</i>	9
2018	Perren and Kozinets	“A lateral exchange market (LEM) as a market that is formed through an intermediating technology platform that facilitates exchange activities among a	<i>Journal of Marketing</i>	47

		network of equivalently positioned economic actors” (p. 21).		
2019	Curtis and Lehner	“Sharing economy for sustainability indicate those sharing practices that promote sustainable consumption compared to purely market-based exchanges” (p. 1).	<i>Sustainability</i>	27
2019	Dellaert	“Consumer coproduction networks as value creation systems in which part of the capital goods and services are provided by individual consumers rather than firms, including consumer co-production that is provided for a commercial purpose” (p. 240).	<i>Journal of the Academy of Marketing Science</i>	20
2019	Eckhardt, Houston, Jiang, Lamberton, Rindfleisch and Zervas	“A scalable socioeconomic system that employs technology-enabled platforms to provide users with temporary access to tangible and intangible resources that may be crowdsourced” (p. 3).	<i>Journal of Marketing</i>	35
2019	Guyader and Piscicelli	“Business and consumption practices that are based on sharing underutilized resources (e.g., goods, services, and spaces) for free or for a fee, typically enabled by online platforms and peer communities” (p. 1060).	<i>Journal of Cleaner Production</i>	10
2019	Wang, Wang, Chai, Wang and Zhang	“A transformative model that has changed the modern human lifestyle and reshaped traditional ways of doing business by combining online and offline resources and serving people by enabling the rental, sharing or exchanging of property without any permanent transfer of ownership” (p. 1011)	<i>Information Technology and People</i>	1
2019	Davlembayeva, Papagiannidis and Alamanos	“The sharing economy is a socio-economic system in which individuals acquire and distribute goods and services among each other for free or for compensation through internet platforms” (p. 1)	<i>Information Technology and People</i>	2

2020	Gao and Li	“The sharing economy constitutes a circular economy that emphasizes sharing and reusing” (p. 2).	<i>Journal of Cleaner Production</i>	1
2020	Gerwe and Silva	“A socioeconomic system that allows peers to grant temporary access to their underutilized physical and human assets through online platforms” (p. 71).	<i>Academy of Management Perspectives</i>	8
2020	Akhmedova, Mas-Machuca, and Marimon	“The sharing economy is an internet-enabled, platform-based and trust-verified interactions of individuals or entities with the goal of providing temporary access or full ownership to idle assets in ex-change for monetary or nonmonetary compensation, that allows management of individual resources in ways that bypass traditional institutions” (p. 1).	<i>Journal of Cleaner Production</i>	0
2020	Govindan, Shankar and Kannan	“An economic system in which assets (man, machine, materials) and/or services are shared between industries (two or more), with the mutual consent with the means of technology” (p. 2).	<i>International Journal of Production Economics</i>	9
2020	Yu, Xu, Yu, Sang, Yang and Jiang	“A new generation of manufacturing that supports shared consumption between individuals by allowing the provision and access of the layered SharedMfg Service (SMS, instances of PSS/CSS/RSS) through a P2P manner” (p. 4).	<i>Computer & Industrial Engineering</i>	0
2020	Sanasi, Ghezzi, Cavallo and Rangone	“The socioeconomic system enabled by digital platforms, where businesses or individuals share and exchange access to tangible and intangible assets; and receive a monetary and/or nonmonetary compensation in return” (p. 4).	<i>Technology Analysis & Strategic Management</i>	5
2020	Berg, Slettemeås,	“Transactions of consumer goods and service between peers, matched and facilitated by	<i>International Journal of Consumer Studies</i>	1

	Kjørstad and Rosenberg	digital platforms” (p. 222).		
2020	Fahmy	“An activity facilitated by digital online platforms where people rent their skills (such as driving) and make their resources (such as properties or cars) available for money” (p. 281).	<i>Journal of Applied Economics</i>	0
2020	Curtis and Mont	“A socio-economic system that leverages technology to mediate two-sided markets, which facilitate temporary access to goods that are under-utilized, tangible, and rivalrous” (p. 4).	<i>Journal of Cleaner Production</i>	3
2020	Hazée, Zwienerber, Van Vaerenbergh, Fasseur, Vandenberghe and Keutgens	“Collaborative consumption involves triadic exchange practices (i.e. platform provider-service provider-customer); the digital platform provider does not own the resources or assets being (temporary) shared and is therefore able to scale up very rapidly; the core service provider is usually a nonprofessional individual (also referred to as “peer service provider”); and interactions between actors must occur to ensure service delivery” (p. 4).	<i>Journal of Service Management</i>	2
2020	Kim and Kim	“The sharing economy is an economic model in which participants share an under-utilized inventory or assets via fee-based sharing between peers” (p. 2814).	<i>Sustainability</i>	1
2020	Zmyślony, Leszczyński, Waligóra and Alejziak	“The sharing economy encompasses business-to-business, business-to-consumer and peer-to-peer initiatives—driven both for-profit and non-profit motivations—which are based on and combine at least three following foundation cores: the <i>platform economy</i> , in terms of intermediating decentralised exchanges among peers	<i>Sustainability</i>	1

		through digital platforms; the <i>access economy</i> , in terms of sharing under-utilized assets to optimize their use, offering services instead of products; the <i>community-based economy</i> , in terms of coordinating initiatives through non-contractual, non-hierarchical or non-monetized forms of interaction” (p. 4).		
2020	Fielbaum and Tirachini	“The exchange of capital, assets, and services between individuals through internet-based platforms for the sharing of underutilised resources at a low transaction cost” (p. 4)	<i>Transportation</i>	0
2020	Lee	“The sharing economy is characterized by peer-to-peer practices in which underused assets or services are acquired, provided, or exchanged for a fee, and organized through community-based online services” (p. 2)	<i>International Journal of Hospitality Management</i>	1
2020	Wu and Yan	“The sharing economy (a.k.a. <i>shareconomy</i> , <i>access</i> , <i>collaborative</i> , and <i>peer economy</i>) refers to a class of economic arrangements in which asset owners and users mutualize access to products or services associated with these assets” (p. 11)	<i>Asian Business and Management</i>	2
2020	Huang and Kuo	“An economic system in which underutilized assets (e.g. property, resources, time and skills) are shared between individuals, either for a fee or for any kind of reciprocity, typically by means of the internet” (p. 806)	<i>Online Information Review</i>	0

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*Citations of definitions from books based on Google Scholar